

SELF- CONCEPT TOWARDS MATHEMATICAL PROFICIENCY OF GRADE 9 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Philippines is now facing one of the major problems when it comes to the result of different international test in which the Philippines garnered the second lowest rank in terms of Mathematics and Science literacy, this was based from the result of PISA 2019. To meet the gap on this situation, this study introduced the self-concept towards Mathematical proficiency that gauged the relation of self- concept that includes academic and non- academic self- concept and mathematical proficiency as to conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, strategic competence, adaptive reasoning and productive disposition. Descriptive- correlational research design was used in attaining the purpose of this study which was administered to seventy (70) grade 9 students from the selected schools in the Division of San Pablo City school year 2020-2021 through the use of questionnaire and Mathematical proficiency test. The result showed a significant relation between the academic self- concept in terms of self- perceived competence as to conceptual understanding and productive disposition. This indicates that self- perceived competence plays a big role in developing the conceptual understanding and productive disposition of students. However, the result also showed that the non- academic self- concept such as physical, social and emotional self- concept has no significant relation to Mathematical proficiency of students. The study suggests that teachers may give more importance in boosting students' academic self- concept as it helps to develop the student's Mathematical proficiency.

Keywords: Mathematical proficiency, Self- concept, Conceptual understanding, Procedural Fluency, Strategic Competence, Adaptive reasoning, Productive disposition